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“Druggability and Genetic Variability at nsp9 Peptide-bound Pockets and Beta-barrel Pockets Across Coronaviruses and SARS-CoV-2 Samples”

Background:

One of the proteins encoded in open reading frame 1a (ORF1a) of many coronaviruses is the non-structural protein 9 (nsp9). Nsp9 is thought to mediate viral replication. In SARS-CoV-1, nsp9’s role has been highlighted as a single-stranded RNA-binding subunit. ([Egloff et al., 2004](#))

The structure of SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 was solved in both apo form and in a peptide-bound form by Litter et al. in July 2020. The peptide identified seemed to originate from a rhinoviral 3C protease sequence (LEVL). The structure of nsp9 is a homodimer and the exogenous peptide is bound at the interface of the two monomers.

Figure 1. The apo and peptide-bound structures of SARS-CoV-2 nsp9. ([Litter et al, 2020](#))

The overall structure of nsp9 is made of a single beta-barrel with an unusual fold originating from serine protease superfamily. (Sutton et al., 2004) The dimerization of nsp9 is mediated via a conserved parallel α -helix containing the "GxxxG" motif. Previous work on nsp9 from SARS-CoV-1 showed the importance of its dimerization for efficient viral growth. Researchers disrupted the dimer formation by mutating the residues at the protein-protein interaction motif (GxxxG) which debilitated the virus. ([Miknis et al., 2009](#))

Considering that nsp9 plays an important role in viral replication, we assessed the druggability of nsp9 pockets and their genetic variability across coronaviruses.

Methods and Results:

Step 1: Assessing the druggability of SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 (PDB:6w9q) with SiteMap.

Using IcmPocketFinder (Molsoft), we identified two pairs of binding pockets on the SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 dimer (PDB code 6w9q): the first pair corresponds to the putative peptide-binding site identified by [Littler et al, 2020](#) (figure 1 & 2). The second pair is within each monomer's beta-barrel and distant from the protein interface (figure 3). Then by applying SiteMap (Schrodinger, NY), we assessed these pockets' druggability using the druggability score (Dscore).

Figure 2. Druggability analysis of SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 peptide-bound pocket. (PDB: 6w9q). The peptides are shown in sticks representation and are occupying the two symmetrical pockets (blue and red) nsp9 shown in ribbon diagram.

Figure 3. Druggability analysis of SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 beta-barrel pocket. (PDB: 6w9q).

Both pockets are druggable; nsp9 peptide-bound pocket has a Dscore of 1.152 and the beta-barrel has a Dscore of 0.956. ([Halgren TA. 2009](#))

Step 2. Determining the residues that line nsp9 pockets.

We determined the sidechains that surround the nsp9 pockets of interest within 2.8 Å. There were 19 residues selected for the peptide-bound pocket, including L4, S5, P6, V7, A8, L9, N33, L42, F75, L88, M101, L103, G104, S105, L106, A107, A108, V110, R111. There were 14 residues selected for the beta-barrel pocket, including M12, C14, A15, D26, R39, F40, V41, R55, F56, P57, K58, S59, I65, T67.

Figure 4. The peptide-bound pocket of nsp9 has 19 surrounding sidechains. (PDB: 6w9q)

Figure 5. The beta-barrel pocket of nsp9 has 14 surrounding sidechains. (PDB: 6w9q)

Step 3. Make diversity dendrograms using nsp9 sequences from the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries downloaded from UniProt database.

We conducted a broad survey of viral proteins from Alpha- and Beta-coronaviruses to identify the most conserved druggable sites. By integrating variability and druggability data, we can then infer the most promising strategies for developing broad-spectrum viral inhibitors. This analysis can be valuable in the context of the emergence of future coronaviruses from circulating viral strains in bat reservoir species. We looked at twenty-seven reviewed nsp9 sequences from Uniprot, where six belong to Alphacoronavirus genus entries, and twenty-one belong to the Betacoronavirus genus. We then assessed the variability of amino acid lining the nsp9 pockets by performing multiple sequence alignment.

We made diversity dendrograms focusing on the 19 sidechains of the peptide-bound pocket (figure 5) and the 14 sidechains of the beta-barrel pocket (figure 6) from step2. In each dendrogram, the consensus profile at each of the sidechain is shown. The colored letters of varying sizes reflect the residues' profile at each amino acid position of interest. The bigger-sized letter is a more commonly found residue at each position.

The % identical residues at peptide-bound pocket is at 26% (53% sequence conservation) and there are no identical residues at the beta-barrel pocket of nsp9 among the entries we have looked at here.

Figure 6. The diversity dendrogram of nsp9 peptide-bound pocket residues across 27 Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera UniProt entries. There are five identical residues at this site including: P6, F75, L88, G104, R111.

Figure 7. The diversity dendrogram of nsp9 beta-barrel pocket residues across 27 Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera UniProt entries. There are no identical residues at this site.

Step 4: Map amino acid identity observed among Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries onto SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 crystal structure (PDB: 6w9q).

We mapped the amino acid variations shown in step 3 onto SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 crystal structure. Sidechains that are non-identical among the entries at the peptide-bound pocket are highlighted in orange and the conserved sidechains are shown in green in figures 7. For the beta-barrel pocket, all fourteen residues (figure 4) were shown to be non-identical.

Figure 8. (A) Color-coded surface representation of SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 Crystal structure (PDB: 6w9q) based on amino acid identity at nsp9 peptide-bound pocket across UniProt entries belonging to Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera. There are five identical residues at this site including: P6, F75, L88, G104, R111. **(B)** The 14 non-identical residues at this site are shown in sticks representation. **(C)** The sideview of surface representation of SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 Crystal structure with the identical and non-identical residues highlighted at the nsp9 peptide-bound pocket.

Step 5: Assessing the amino acid variability of nsp9 peptide-bound pocket among SARS-CoV-2 samples.

Nicola De Maio, our collaborator from Nick Goldman's lab at the European Bioinformatics Institute, looked at more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples from COVID-19 patients and identified all mutations at the nsp9 pockets.

He identified 11 non-synonymous variants at 9 unique amino acid positions of the nsp9 peptide-bound pocket site as shown in table 1. For example, at residue 101, the wild-type sidechain in SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 is methionine(M). In the sample batch Nicola has looked at, he also identified two other variants including M101I and M101V. While these two mutations are rather conserved since M, I and V all have hydrophobic sidechains, mutations at other positions are may be more disruptive: for instance, G104R. The source of each of the variants and its description are also noted in table 1.

In table 2, we show the non-synonymous variants at the beta-barrel pocket of nsp9. There were 4 non-synonymous variants identified at 4 unique amino acid positions of the SARS-CoV-2 nsp9 beta-barrel pocket.

Index	Wild type amino acid in SARS-Cov-2	Non-synonymous variants	Codon one	Codon two	Codon three	Source of the variants
1	L4	L (15873)	c (15873)	t (15875)	t (15875)	F variant from Turkey, EPI_ISL_437331.
		1 F (1)	t (1)			
2	L42	L (15869)	c (15869)	t (15875)	c (1)	The 6 N variants are found in the USA and Turkey, apparently following a single mutation event.
		2 F (6)	t (6)			
3	F75	F (15874)	t (15875)	t (15875)	t (15874)	L variant found in California, EPI_ISL_436654.
		3 L (1)			a (1)	
4	M101	M (15869)	a (15871)	t (15874)	g (15872)	The 3 V variants are found in Spain, apparently following a single mutation event. The 2 I variants are found in Wales and USA, apparently following 2 distinct mutation events.
		4 I (2)	g (3)		t (2)	
		5 V (3)				
5	L103	L (15873)	c (15873)	t (15874)	t (15875)	F variant found in USA, EPI_ISL_436052.
		6 F (1)	t (1)			
6	G104	G (15874)	g (15874)	g (15875)	t (15875)	R variant found in Russia, EPI_ISL_415710.
		7 R (1)	c (1)			
7	S105	S (15874)	a (15874)	g (15875)	t (15875)	G variant found in England, EPI_ISL_433684.
		8 G (1)	g (1)			
8	L106	L (15873)	t (15875)	t (15873)	a (15875)	S variant found in Belgium, EPI_ISL_42035.
		9 S (1)		c (1)		
9	A107	A (15872)	g (15874)	c (15874)	t (15815)	V variant from USA, EPI_ISL_430342. S variant from England, EPI_ISL_441735.
		10 S (1)	t (1)	t (1)		
		11 V (1)				

Table 1. Eleven Non-synonymous variants observed at nsp9 peptide-bound pocket amino acid residues across over 15000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples from COVID-19 patients.

Index	Wild type amino acid in SARS-Cov-2	Non-synonymous variants	Codon one	Codon two	Codon three	Source of the variants
1	A15	A (15871)	g (15875)	c (15871) t (4)	t (15875)	4 V variants from USA, apparently from a single mutation event.
		1 V (4)				
2	R55	R (15870)	a (15873)	a (1) g (15871)	a (15872)	K variant from Spain, EPI_ISL_428711.
		2 K (1)				
3	P57	P (15869)	c (15869) t (4)	c (15873)	t (15873)	4 S variants from Scotland, USA, Australia, and Northern Ireland, apparently from 4 different mutation events.
		3 S (4)				
4	T67	T (15871)	a (15875)	c (15871) t (4)	a (15875)	4 I variants from England, Scotland, and Denmark, apparently from a single mutation event.
		4 I (4)				

Table 2. Four Non-synonymous variants observed at nsp9 beta-barrel pocket amino acid residues across over 15000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples from COVID-19 patients.

Conclusion:

Our analysis shows that the nsp9 peptide-bound pocket which is at the interface of the two nsp9 monomers is more druggable than the beta-barrel pocket of nsp9. We see that the peptide-bound pocket has relatively low amino acid identity at 26% while the beta-barrel pocket has none. In a similar fashion, SARS-CoV-2 non-synonymous mutations are frequent at both sites (9 out of 19 residues for the peptide-bound pocket, 4 out of 14 residues for the beta-barrel pocket). In summary, our data discourages the design of broad-spectrum inhibitors against nsp9 peptide-bound pockets and beta-barrel pockets.

References

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